

The foamForNuclear Python API for Accessible Multi-physics Reactor Simulations with GeN-Foam and OFFBEAT

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ABSTRACT

Developed in the context of the foamForNuclear project, which unifies and extends the capabilities of the OpenFOAM-based solvers GeN-Foam and OFFBEAT, this work presents the foamForNuclear Python API, a new interface designed to simplify the use of GeN-Foam and OFFBEAT for multi-physics reactor and fuel performance simulations. While these solvers offer advanced coupling between neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and thermo-mechanics, their steep learning curve and reliance on complex OpenFOAM dictionaries limit accessibility. The Python API lowers this barrier by providing intuitive, scriptable workflows for case setup, solver coupling, and post-processing, while ensuring compatibility with standard OpenFOAM structures. Examples illustrate how the API enables explicit and reproducible coupling declarations, systematic solver loop management, and robust integration with Monte Carlo codes within research-grade multi-physics workflows. By bridging modern Python ecosystems with advanced nuclear solvers, the foamForNuclear Python API enables more transparent, reproducible, and efficient simulation workflows.

Keywords: Python API, Multi-physics, foamForNuclear, OpenFOAM

1. MOTIVATION

In recent developments, the open-source multi-physics codes GeN-Foam [1] and OFFBEAT [2] have been integrated into the broader foamForNuclear (FFN) project [3]. OFFBEAT continues to serve as the dedicated fuel-behaviour code, while GeN-Foam has evolved into the application responsible for coupling all FFN libraries in a flexible and general way. Although GeN-Foam and OFFBEAT represent powerful tools for coupled multi-physics simulations in nuclear reactor analysis, they remain unusually complex compared to standard OpenFOAM solvers [4]. Both codes involve a large number of sub-models, solver configurations, and physical parameters. Their multidimensional, fully coupled nature, spanning neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and thermo-mechanics, makes them highly capable, but also introduces a steep learning curve, particularly for new users or researchers unfamiliar with the internal structure of OpenFOAM. This complexity, although scientifically justified, currently limits the routine use of these tools in systematic studies, large-scale parametric campaigns, uncertainty quantification, and reproducible research workflows.

In recent years, there has been a growing demand from the user community, especially among young nuclear engineers and researchers, for a more accessible Python-based interface. Python [5] has become a standard high-level language for orchestrating scientific simulations and has gained popularity due to its simplicity, readability, and rich ecosystem of scientific libraries for data analysis, visualization, optimization, and machine learning. The success of Python-driven tools such as OpenMC [6, 7] illustrates how a well-designed interface can greatly improve usability and adoption while supporting research-grade scientific applications.

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In addition to lowering the entry barrier for new users, a Python interface plays a critical role in enabling streamlined code transitions between different modeling approaches. For instance, one may use the Python package Workflow and Template Toolkit for Simulation (Watts) [8] to parametrize and execute Serpent input [9] and generate multi-group cross sections (MGXS) that can be seamlessly transferred to the foamForNuclear neutronics sub-solver, or employ OpenMC to provide power distribution for multi-physics simulations in GeN-Foam. Conversely, field data such as temperature or density distributions produced in the foamForNuclear sub-solvers, such as thermal-hydraulics or thermal-mechanics, can be extracted and fed back into Monte Carlo calculations, improving the fidelity of heterogeneous reactor analyses. Such bidirectional coupling workflows are increasingly central to contemporary reactor studies and safety analyses. Beyond data exchange, Python also provides a natural environment for integrating machine learning frameworks such as PyTorch [10], allowing optimization, sensitivity studies, and advanced parameter estimation workflows to be expressed in compact scripts.

In this context, the development of a dedicated Python Application Programming Interface (API) for GeN-Foam and OFFBEAT through the FFN project is proposed. This interface aims to formalize case generation and solver configuration in a programmatic form that supports automation, verification, and reproducibility, improve documentation through inline display in modern text editors such as VSCode, and support intuitive scripting workflows. The initial criteria include ease of installation, extensibility, inline documentation, and compatibility with existing GeN-Foam/OFFBEAT workflows, with the long-term goal of lowering barriers to entry and enhancing scientific productivity.

2. STRUCTURE OF AN OPENFOAM CASE USING THE FFN PYTHON API

The foamForNuclear Python API is designed to closely mirror the structure and logic of GeN-Foam and OFFBEAT, which itself inherits from the foundational principles of OpenFOAM cases. To maintain familiarity and ease of use, the API adopts the same class naming conventions as those found in the C++ source code, allowing users to transition seamlessly between the Python interface and the underlying implementation. While preserving this conceptual structure, the API introduces a simplified and streamlined object hierarchy, making it easier to navigate and configure multi-physics models that have evolved over years of development.

Each physical model within the foamForNuclear framework is represented by a dedicated Python class, supporting modular configuration and inline documentation through Python's standard docstring conventions. This facilitates both code transparency and automatic documentation generation.

Installation follows standard Python practices via the `pip` utility, the most common package management tool in the Python ecosystem. Although installation currently requires cloning from the project repository [11], future versions are intended to be distributed through mainstream Python repositories, alongside well-known packages such as NumPy [12], Matplotlib [13], or PyTorch.

In parallel with the development of the foamForNuclear Python API, a dedicated documentation framework has been established using Sphinx [14], a widely adopted tool in the Python community for generating structured, searchable, and cross-referenced documentation. While Sphinx is most commonly employed for scientific libraries such as NumPy or Matplotlib, its application to the nuclear multi-physics domain provides a significant benefit by unifying API references, solver-specific guidelines, and formal usage documentation required for long-term maintainability and reproducible studies in a consistent and navigable format. Automatically extracting Python docstrings and C++ headers from the codebase ensures that the documentation remains synchronized with the implementation, reducing maintenance overhead and improving reliability for end-users.

The API is also being developed as a foundation for migrating and extending Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) -related functionalities [15], including the multi-Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU) implicit solver presented in Ref. [16] and tools for generating FMUs directly from OpenFOAM cases, expanding its utility for real-time simulation and co-simulation workflows.

Figure 1. Comparison of case structure between the new foamForNuclear Python API (left) and the standard OpenFOAM case structure applied to GeN-Foam (right).

The foamForNuclear Python API provides a streamlined and scriptable interface for setting up and executing OpenFOAM-based simulations. The API formalizes the sequence of operations required for creating and executing a multi-physics case, including:

- Mesh generation for each physical region;
- Initialization of field values within time folders;
- Definition and configuration of sub-solvers (e.g., neutronics, thermal-hydraulics);
- Declaration of field couplings between solvers;
- Specification of global model parameters (e.g., end time, time step);
- Execution of preprocessing utilities;
- Running the simulation; and
- Performing post-processing to extract and visualize results.

The mesh generation step can be carried out using an extended version of the blockMesh utility, adapted to handle geometrical features commonly encountered in reactor modeling, such as hexagonal lattices and wedge-type domains. Alternatively, meshes can be imported via polyMesh folders, generated via Gmsh [17], or converted from Salome [18] using the ideasUnvToFoam tool, providing flexibility in geometry creation and preprocessing. The API enables users to instantiate solvers through predefined high-level classes that represent common physics domains, such as neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, or OFFBEAT-based thermo-mechanics, thereby significantly reducing the complexity of solver configuration and providing more accessible entry points for new users.

Figure 1 compares the file and folder hierarchy of a standard GeN-Foam multi-physics case with the

single-script organization offered by the foamForNuclear Python API. In a common OpenFOAM setup, information is distributed across numerous nested files and directories, with no obvious entry point for new users. This scattered structure often complicates both case understanding and subsequent modifications. By contrast, the Python API reduces the workflow to a single script that guides the user through each step, mesh generation, field declaration, solver parametrization, execution, and post-processing, in a clear and linear fashion. This script centralizes all essential input parameters and provides an explicit, version-controllable definition of the full simulation workflow, improving traceability, reproducibility, and peer review of computational studies.

3. APPLICATION EXAMPLES

3.1. General example

To illustrate the capabilities of the foamForNuclear Python API, a first example demonstrates the setup and execution of a basic neutronics diffusion problem using GeN-Foam. The workflow, summarized in Listing 1, highlights the streamlined process of going from geometry preparation to result extraction. The case is designed to remain compact while demonstrating a complete research-oriented workflow, while still showcasing the interoperability with external Monte Carlo tools.

The setup begins by importing a mesh from an existing OpenFOAM polyMesh folder, corresponding to a predefined neutronic region. Initial conditions are then created in a dedicated time folder. For instance, the neutron flux field is initialized with a uniform internal value and boundary conditions that combine zero-gradient and fixed-value treatments.

Next, the neutronics solver is instantiated through a high-level class, specifying solver type, mesh, global parameters such as power, and an initial k_{eff} estimate. The solver uses multi-group cross sections (MGXS) generated by Serpent [9], which are read directly through the API. In this example, one Serpent universe is mapped to a mesh zone with a prescribed fuel volume fraction, showcasing how the API facilitates data exchange between a Monte Carlo code and the neutronics sub-solver. The nuclear data are stored in a structured state object, which can be extended to handle multiple operating conditions, such as different temperatures or coolant densities, if they have already been computed.

The model settings are defined via the standard OpenFOAM control dictionary, here expressed in Python syntax with attributes such as end time, time step, and output control. This approach preserves OpenFOAM logic while improving readability through Python's object-oriented structure. Once configured, the model can be exported to the OpenFOAM directory structure with a single function call (`model.export_to_openfoam()`).

Finally, the case is executed through a one-line command, calling the GeN-Foam application, and the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} is extracted. The entire process, from mesh import and cross-section extraction to solver execution and post-processing, is expressed in fewer than 50 lines of code, enabling rapid iteration, parametric variation, and systematic study execution. This compactness highlights the efficiency of the API and its ability to bridge Monte Carlo data generation, multi-physics solvers, and post-processing within a single Python-driven workflow.

3.2. Multi-physics coupling example

A second example highlights the ease with which multi-physics couplings can be expressed within the foamForNuclear Python API. Listing 2 shows how the neutronics and thermal-hydraulics sub-solvers of foamForNuclear are linked through a dedicated Coupling object, designed to manage inter-solver communication in a transparent and modular way. This encapsulation abstracts much of the complexity typically associated with coupling physics in GeN-Foam, while retaining full control over the fields exchanged.

Listing 1. Example of use of the foamForNuclear Python API to create and run a simple neutronics case.

```
1 import foamForNuclear as ffn
2 import foamForNuclear.boundaryConditions as bc
3 import foamForNuclear.mesh as mesh
4
5 # Mesh
6 nMesh = mesh.PolyMesh(srcpath="./polyMesh", region="neutroRegion", isOverwrite=True)
7
8 # Fields
9 timeFolder0 = ffn.TimeFolder(0)
10
11 defaultFlux = ffn.Field("defaultFlux", region=nMesh.region)
12 defaultFlux.dimensions = ffn.Dimension(default="flux")
13 defaultFlux.internalField = 1e21
14 defaultFlux.set_boundary_condition("walls", bc.ZeroGradient())
15 defaultFlux.set_boundary_condition("top", bc.FixedValue(0))
16 defaultFlux.set_boundary_condition("bottom", bc.FixedValue(0))
17
18 timeFolder0.append(defaultFlux)
19
20 # Solver
21 neutronicsSolver = ffn.NeutronicsSolver(
22     solver="diffusionNeutronics",
23     mesh=nMesh,
24     region=nMesh.region,
25     power=10e+06,
26     keff=1.0
27 )
28 refState = ffn.NuclearDataState("reference")
29 refState.read_from_serpent(
30     outputFilename="Serpent/main_res.m",
31     universes=[
32         # SSS2    OpenFOAM    fuelFraction
33         ("uFuel", "fuel", 0.3)
34     ]
35 )
36 neutronicsSolver.nuclearData.add_state(refState)
37
38 # Settings
39 model = ffn.Model(timeFolders=[timeFolder0])
40 model.solvers.append(neutronicsSolver)
41
42 settings: ffn.ControlDict = model.settings
43 settings.application = "GeN-Foam"
44 settings.endTime = 1
45 settings.deltaT = 1e-9
46 settings.writeControl = "adjustableRunTime"
47 settings.writeInterval = 1
48 settings.runTimeModifiable = True
49 settings.adjustTimeStep = True
50
51 print(model)
52
53 # Export to OpenFOAM
54 model.export_to_openfoam()
55
56 # Run
57 ffn.run(model=model)
58
59 # Post-processing
60 print(f"keff = {model.keff()}")
```

Listing 2. Example of coupling between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics solvers using the foamForNuclear Python API.

```
1 import foamForNuclear as ffn
2
3 # Mesh, fields, solvers creation ...
4
5 # Solvers
6 solvers = ffn.Solvers([neutronicsSolver, thSolver])
7
8 # Coupling
9 coupling = ffn.Coupling(solvers)
10
11 coupling.add_field_transfer(neutronicsSolver, thSolver, "powerDensity", "powerDensityNeutronics")
12
13 coupling.add_field_transfer(thSolver, neutronicsSolver, "T", "TCool")
14 coupling.add_field_transfer(thSolver, neutronicsSolver, "thermo:rho", "rhoCool")
15 coupling.add_field_transfer(thSolver, neutronicsSolver, "T.fuelAvForNeutronics", "TFuel")
16 coupling.add_field_transfer(thSolver, neutronicsSolver, "T.cladAvForNeutronics", "TClad")
17 coupling.add_field_transfer(thSolver, neutronicsSolver, "T.passiveStructure", "TStructMech")
18
19 # Settings
20 model = ffn.Model(
21     solvers=solvers,
22     coupling=coupling,
23     timeFolders=[timeFolder0]
24 )
25 model.coupling.plot_coupling_graph()
26 model.coupling.plot_solving_graph()
27 model.coupling.plot_solving_flowchart()
```

In this example, the coupling is initialized by passing the solver list to the Coupling object, after which a series of field transfers is explicitly declared. The neutronics solver provides the local power density to the thermal-hydraulics solver, while the latter returns thermal-hydraulic quantities essential for neutronic feedback. These include the coolant temperature, density, and averaged fuel, cladding, and passive structures temperatures. Each transfer is defined with clear source and target regions and field names, enabling the workflow to remain readable and extensible. Such a structure allows new physics modules to be integrated with minimal overhead while making the coupling logic self-documenting.

For verification and transparency, the API includes dedicated plotting utilities that automatically generate coupling graphs, solver resolution diagrams, and flowcharts. These visualizations allow the user to confirm that the data exchanges are consistent with the intended physics, and they also provide a verification and transparency mechanism for validating solver interactions in complex multi-physics configurations.

3.3. Multi-physics loop example

The foamForNuclear Python API also supports the definition of iterative solver loops, which are essential for tackling conjugate heat transfer (CHT) and other tightly coupled multi-physics problems. Listing 3 demonstrates how a CHT loop can be declared in just a few lines, encapsulating the fluid and solid solvers in a dedicated iterative structure. This design abstracts the complexity of setting up nested sub-solver loops, while providing users with precise control over convergence criteria and solver ordering.

In this example, the CHTLoop object is instantiated with both the fluid and solid solvers, along with user-defined parameters such as minimum residual tolerance, maximum iteration count, and explicit specification of interface patches between regions. Similar constructs are available for Picard iterations and fluid-structure interaction (FSI) loops, enabling tailored resolution strategies for a broad range of

Listing 3. Example of conjugate heat transfer coupling between thermal-mechanics and thermal-hydraulics solvers using the foamForNuclear Python API.

```
1 import foamForNuclear as ffn
2
3 solvers = ffn.Solvers([fluidSolver, solidSolver])
4
5 chtLoop = ffn.CHTLoop(
6     region="Level_1",
7     solvers=[fluidSolver, solidSolver],
8     minResidual=1e-6,
9     maxIterations=100,
10    fluidRegionName=fluidSolver.region, solidRegionName=solidSolver.region,
11    fluidPatches=[fluidInterface.name], solidPatches=[solidTop.name],
12    useHTC=False
13 )
14
15 coupling = ffn.Coupling(solvers=[chtLoop])
```

multi-physics scenarios.

4. DISCUSSION

The foamForNuclear Python API represents a significant step toward making advanced multi-physics solvers such as GeN-Foam and OFFBEAT more accessible to a wider community of users. By lowering the entry barrier through an intuitive scripting interface, the API simplifies the setup and preparation of complex coupled simulations, accelerates the transition from external tool data to multi-physics workflows, and integrates seamlessly with modern Python-based tools for optimization, sensitivity analysis, and machine learning. This new abstraction layer is expected to broaden adoption while enabling reproducible, auditable, and scalable multi-physics simulation studies.

At the same time, the introduction of a Python interface inevitably raises questions of scope and maintainability. The API must ensure full compliance with OpenFOAM conventions to produce valid and reliable case files, which in turn may influence the structure of the foamForNuclear sub-solver dictionaries themselves. While the current implementation already supports the most important functionalities, extending coverage to include the complete set of OpenFOAM's `functionObjects`, boundary conditions, and solver options will require sustained development effort. Another critical milestone is the integration of full case reading using the `foamLib` Python package, allowing existing OpenFOAM cases to be directly imported and manipulated without recreating full Python input scripts, a feature particularly valuable for parametric and sensitivity studies. Together, these developments position the API not merely as a convenience layer, but as a core research infrastructure for advanced nuclear multi-physics simulation workflows.

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